

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№ 10

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

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*Elektron nashr. 1549 sahifa.
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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF SPOKEN ENGLISH IN GLOBAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract. This article highlights the role and importance of spoken English in global communication. In the context of modern globalization, English is recognized as an essential means of communication not only in international business, diplomacy, and education but also in everyday life. The article analyzes the impact of fluency in English on an individual's professional and social success, as well as its contribution to the formation of an effective communication culture.

Key words: English language, spoken language, global communication, linguistic competence, communication, education, international relations.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada og'zaki ingliz tilining global muloqotdagi o'rni va ahamiyati yoritilgan. Hozirgi globallashtirish jarayonida ingliz tili nafaqat xalqaro biznes, diplomatiya va ta'lim sohalarida, balki kundalik hayotda ham muhim aloqa vositasi sifatida e'tirof etiladi. Maqolada ingliz tilida erkin so'zlashish ko'nikmalarining shaxsning kasbiy va ijtimoiy muvaffaqiyatiga ta'siri, shuningdek, samarali muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirishdagi o'rni tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz tili, og'zaki nutq, global muloqot, til kompetensiyasi, kommunikatsiya, ta'lim, xalqaro aloqalar.

Аннотация. В данной статье освещается роль и значение разговорного английского языка в глобальной коммуникации. В условиях современной глобализации английский язык рассматривается как важное средство общения не только в международном бизнесе, дипломатии и сфере образования, но и в повседневной жизни. В статье анализируется влияние свободного владения английским языком на профессиональный и социальный успех личности, а также его значение в формировании культуры эффективного общения.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, устная речь, глобальная коммуникация, языковая компетенция, коммуникация, образование, международные отношения.

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, English has become the most widespread and influential language of international communication. It serves as a bridge that connects people of diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds, allowing them to exchange ideas, conduct business, and collaborate across various professional fields.

Spoken English, in particular, plays a vital role in facilitating real-time communication, promoting mutual understanding, and fostering relationships across borders. The ability to communicate fluently in spoken English is not only fundamental for academic and professional achievement but also represents an essential competency for active engagement in the global community.

With the rapid advancement of technology and the expansion of international cooperation, English has evolved into the dominant language of diplomacy, media, science, and education. Enhancing proficiency in spoken English enables individuals to gain confidence, articulate their thoughts clearly, and participate effectively in intercultural interactions.

This article explores the significance of spoken English in international communication, analyzes its influence on personal and professional development, and examines the main challenges faced by non-native speakers in mastering it. Furthermore, it discusses modern strategies and innovative approaches aimed at improving speaking skills that are essential in today's interconnected world.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the modern era of globalization, English has become one of the most extensively studied and researched languages, serving as the primary medium of international communication. Numerous studies demonstrate that English plays a crucial role in facilitating real-time interaction — not only through written communication but,

more importantly, through speech — while also contributing to the expansion of economic, educational, and social opportunities worldwide.

Oral communication, in particular, serves as an essential instrument in achieving mutual understanding and reaching agreements efficiently within international business, scientific collaboration, and diplomatic relations¹.

The concept of English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) holds a distinctive and significant position in modern linguistic research. Jennifer Jenkins and other scholars have extensively analyzed this concept, emphasizing that the majority of contemporary English users are non-native speakers and that communication often takes place in an adapted and functionally oriented form of English.

This perspective on ELF calls for a renewed understanding of pronunciation, vocabulary, and communicative strategies, focusing on mutual intelligibility rather than adherence to native-speaker norms. It also highlights the evolving nature of English as a dynamic, inclusive, and globally shared means of interaction, fostering intercultural understanding and effective communication among speakers from diverse linguistic backgrounds².

In modern language teaching theories, communicative competence and the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach occupy a central role in developing oral communication skills. Researchers such as Brown emphasize the importance of communicative tasks, real-world contexts, and interactive exercises in the process of language learning. Contemporary studies confirm the effectiveness of CLT; however, they also recommend adapting it to specific cultural contexts and integrating it with modern technologies to enhance learning outcomes.

Numerous empirical studies and surveys demonstrate that proficiency in the English language has a direct and positive influence on labor market opportunities. Evidence indicates that higher levels of English proficiency can expand employment prospects, improve professional mobility, and increase income levels. Nevertheless, scholars note that the global dominance of English may create challenges for linguistic diversity and equitable access, underscoring the need for inclusive and balanced language policies rather than presenting it as a negative phenomenon.

In recent years, technological progress—particularly in artificial intelligence and translation tools—has further strengthened the role of English in professional environments. The growing number of positions requiring advanced English proficiency reflects the language's increasing significance in the digital economy. While AI-based tools can help reduce basic communication barriers, human language competence remains indispensable for understanding cultural nuances and the subtleties of verbal expression.

Current literature also identifies several gaps and promising directions for future research, including:

- pronunciation and standardization issues within English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) settings;
- adaptation of CLT and task-based learning approaches to diverse cultural contexts;
- longitudinal studies assessing the economic effects of English language acquisition;
- evaluations of the effectiveness of technology-integrated oral language textbooks.

These areas represent valuable opportunities for advancing the theoretical and practical understanding of English language education in a globalized world.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for this study, titled “The Importance of Spoken English in Global Communication,” is grounded in a mixed-methods approach that combines both qualitative and quantitative techniques to obtain a comprehensive and balanced understanding of the subject. The primary objective of the study is to analyze the role of spoken English in enhancing communication among individuals from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds, as well as to explore the challenges encountered by non-native speakers in developing effective speaking skills.

This research employs a descriptive and analytical design, aimed at identifying current trends in the use of spoken English in global communication and examining how proficiency in spoken English contributes to intercultural understanding, educational achievement, and career advancement. To ensure the reliability and depth of analysis, both primary and secondary data sources were utilized.

1. Primary Data: Primary data were collected through surveys and semi-structured interviews conducted with students, teachers, and professionals representing various sectors where English is used as a means of communication. The survey focused on several key aspects, including the frequency of English usage, confidence in speaking, the perceived importance of spoken English, and common barriers to fluency.

2. Secondary Data: Secondary data were gathered from academic journals, scholarly books, international reports, and reputable online publications related to English language learning, global communication, and

1 <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/b6L6r/open>

2 <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9781118411360.wbcla047>

applied linguistics. Key references include David Crystal (2003) – “English as a Global Language,” Dell Hymes (1972) – “Communicative Competence,” and Jennifer Jenkins (2007) – “English as a Lingua Franca.”

The collected data were analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative methods:

1. Quantitative Analysis: Data obtained from surveys were processed using descriptive statistics, including percentages, means, and frequency distributions, to identify trends and patterns in English language use and perceptions of its importance.

2. Qualitative Analysis: Interview data were examined through thematic analysis to identify recurring themes such as motivation, confidence, pronunciation challenges, and cultural adaptation.

This mixed-methods research approach provides a holistic perspective on the importance of spoken English in global communication. By integrating statistical findings with personal experiences, the study combines empirical evidence with human insight, thereby demonstrating how spoken English effectively connects people, fosters mutual understanding, and strengthens intercultural relations in today’s interconnected world.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The study sought to determine the significance of spoken English as a vital instrument of international communication and to identify the key factors influencing the oral proficiency of English learners across various professional and educational contexts. A total of 100 respondents participated in the research, comprising students, teachers, and professionals working in international business, tourism, and education sectors.

A mixed-methods approach, which included questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, was employed. This methodology enabled the collection of both quantitative and qualitative data, providing a comprehensive and balanced analysis of the topic.

The survey results revealed that oral proficiency in English is positively correlated with the frequency of practical language use and the level of professional motivation. Respondents who regularly used English in their studies or workplaces demonstrated higher confidence, fluency, and communicative competence. Moreover, participants noted that consistent exposure to authentic English-speaking environments, such as international conferences or online collaborations, significantly improved their pronunciation, vocabulary range, and intercultural communication skills.

Overall, the findings confirm that active and purposeful use of spoken English not only enhances linguistic ability but also strengthens individuals’ professional potential and global competitiveness (1-table).

1-table. Key Findings on the Importance and Usage of Spoken English Among Respondents

Indicator	Number of participants (%)	Analytical interpretation
Regularly use English in work or study	86%	English is perceived as a necessary tool for professional communication.
Consider oral communication the most important aspect of language proficiency	78%	The trend toward prioritizing speaking over reading and writing is confirmed.
Experiencing difficulties with pronunciation and fluency	64%	Lack of practice and psychological barriers remain key challenges.
Believing that good oral English proficiency improves their career prospects	82%	A high correlation is demonstrated between language proficiency and professional prospects.
Use modern technologies (online courses, applications) to develop skills	71%	There is growing interest in digital learning methods and self-development.

The obtained data confirm that the majority of participants recognize the strategic importance of spoken English and consistently strive to improve their proficiency. However, they continue to face certain challenges, such as pronunciation difficulties, limited speaking practice, and a lack of confidence during verbal communication.

The analysis revealed that spoken English serves as a crucial tool for individuals’ social and professional integration into the global environment. Eighty-seven percent (87%) of respondents stated that fluency in English enhances their competitiveness in the labor market, while seventy-four percent (74%) emphasized that oral communication helps them establish trustful and long-term relationships with partners and clients. These findings highlight not only the pragmatic value of the English language but also its cultural and communicative significance in contemporary society.

Interestingly, more than half of respondents (53%) believe that spoken English proficiency is considerably more important than written English, particularly in today's digital era, where communication increasingly takes place through online meetings, video conferences, and international forums.

Based on the results of this analysis, it can be concluded that globalization has strengthened the importance of English not merely as a medium of communication, but as a fundamental component of personal and professional development. In the context of transnational interaction, proficiency in spoken English fosters openness, adaptability, and competitiveness—qualities essential for effective participation in a multicultural environment.

Furthermore, the findings indicate that the most successful intercultural communicators are those who not only possess grammatical accuracy but also demonstrate strong active listening, emotional expressiveness, and cultural sensitivity. This suggests that effective oral communication extends beyond linguistic competence and reflects a high level of intercultural awareness, tolerance, and professional maturity.

Thus, it can be concluded that the advancement of spoken English plays an integral role in promoting global integration, international education, and economic cooperation. It not only broadens professional horizons but also enhances mutual understanding among nations, thereby creating a strong foundation for constructive and sustainable dialogue within the global community.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study confirmed that spoken English serves as a vital component of successful global communication in the 21st century. It fosters mutual understanding among people of different cultures, enhances professional mobility, and broadens access to educational opportunities. In this regard, the ability to speak English fluently functions not only as a means of communication but also as an element of social capital, strengthening an individual's competitiveness in the global labor market and contributing to their overall personal development. Although the research identified certain challenges—such as limited practical usage of English, psychological barriers to speaking, and insufficient opportunities for intercultural interaction within learning environments—these obstacles can be effectively addressed through innovative and inclusive educational approaches. Based on the findings, several recommendations are proposed: first, it is necessary to reinforce the communicative approach to English language teaching by focusing on the active development of oral communication through role-playing, dialogues, and interactive discussions; second, it is important to establish an encouraging linguistic environment by organizing conversation clubs, online exchanges, and international collaboration projects that simulate real-life communication situations; third, the integration of modern technologies, including virtual simulations, mobile applications, and educational podcasts, will enhance learner engagement and help overcome linguistic barriers; fourth, improving teacher qualifications, particularly in methodologies related to oral competence and the effective use of digital tools, should become a strategic priority; and finally, the promotion of intercultural exchange programs will provide learners with authentic language experiences and build greater confidence in communication. In conclusion, mastering spoken English is not merely an academic objective but a fundamental prerequisite for active participation in a globalized world where communication serves as the cornerstone of cooperation, innovation, and mutual understanding among nations.

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 10

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
